

Teaching Practices of Public Senior High School Teachers of 21st-Century Skills In San Carlos City Division

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Abstract

The integration of 21st-century skills in education emphasizes the development of learners who are critical thinkers, effective communicators, collaborative problem-solvers, and digitally literate individuals prepared for lifelong learning. This study was conducted to assess the extent of practices of teaching 21st-century skills among Senior High School teachers in District V-A, San Carlos City Division, for the School Year 2024–2025. Specifically, it sought to determine the level of implementation of 21st-century skills in the areas of learning skills, innovation skills, information and media skills, digital literacy skills, life skills, and career skills.

The study employed a descriptive research design with Senior High School teachers and school heads as respondents. A researcher-made questionnaire served as the primary data-gathering instrument, while weighted mean and t-test were used to analyze the data.

Findings revealed that both teachers and school heads perceived the extent of practices of teaching 21st-century skills as moderately practiced across all domains. Results further showed no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and school heads, indicating a shared understanding of the implementation of 21st-century skills in instructional practices. Moreover, the problems encountered in implementing these skills were rated as moderately serious, highlighting the need for continuous professional development, improved access to resources, and stronger institutional support.

In conclusion, the teaching of 21st-century skills among Senior High School teachers in the district is generally evident but requires further enhancement. The findings of the study serve as a basis for designing an action plan aimed at strengthening instructional practices and ensuring effective integration of 21st-century skills in Senior High School classrooms.

Keywords: *21st-Century Skills, Teaching Practices, Senior High School Teachers, Digital Literacy, Life and Career Skills*

INTRODUCTION

Education in the 21st century demands instructional practices that go beyond content mastery and focus on equipping learners with essential skills needed to thrive in a rapidly changing, knowledge-based society. These skills include critical thinking, creativity, collaboration,

communication, digital literacy, adaptability, and career readiness. Collectively referred to as 21st-century skills, these competencies are vital in preparing learners to meet the challenges of globalization, technological advancement, and workforce demands.

The Department of Education (DepEd) emphasizes the integration of 21st-century skills across the K–12 curriculum, particularly at the Senior High School level, where learners are prepared for higher education, employment, and entrepreneurship. Effective teaching of these skills requires innovative instructional strategies, meaningful use of technology, learner-centered approaches, and authentic assessment practices. Studies have shown that when teachers effectively integrate 21st-century skills into instruction, learners demonstrate improved academic performance, higher engagement, and enhanced problem-solving and decision-making abilities.

Despite policy support and curriculum alignment, the effective implementation of 21st-century skills in classrooms remains a challenge. Issues such as limited access to ICT resources, insufficient training, large class sizes, and time constraints often hinder teachers from fully integrating these skills into their daily teaching practices. Moreover, discrepancies in perceptions between teachers and school leaders regarding implementation may affect instructional coherence and support mechanisms.

Grounded in the need to strengthen instructional practices aligned with contemporary educational demands, this study aimed to assess the extent of practices of teaching 21st-century skills among Senior High School teachers in public secondary schools. Specifically, it sought to determine the level of implementation across key skill domains, examine differences in perceptions between teachers and school heads, and identify problems encountered in teaching these skills. The study hypothesized that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and school heads regarding the extent of practices of teaching 21st-century skills. The results of this study are expected to provide insights that may guide school leaders and policymakers in enhancing professional development programs and instructional support systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a **descriptive research design** to assess the extent of practices of teaching 21st-century skills among Senior High School teachers. The design was appropriate for describing existing instructional practices, examining perceptions of teachers and school heads, and identifying challenges encountered in integrating 21st-century skills without manipulating variables.

Participants

The participants of the study consisted of a **total enumeration** of **115 Senior High School teachers and 9 school heads** from public secondary schools in District V-A, San Carlos City

Division. The respondents were selected due to their direct involvement in planning, implementing, and supervising instructional practices related to the teaching of 21st-century skills.

Instruments

A **researcher-made questionnaire** was used as the primary data-gathering instrument. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part I measured the extent of practices of teaching 21st-century skills across six domains: learning skills, innovation skills, information and media skills, digital literacy skills, life skills, and career skills. Part II assessed the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by teachers in implementing these skills. A Likert-scale format was used to quantify respondents' perceptions.

Procedure

Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the respondents in their respective schools. Respondents were informed of the purpose of the study and assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Data collection was completed within two weeks, with a 100% retrieval rate of questionnaires.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, specifically **weighted mean**, were used to determine the extent of practices of teaching 21st-century skills. The **t-test** was employed to determine whether a significant difference existed between the perceptions of teachers and school heads at a 0.05 level of significance. The degree of seriousness of problems encountered was analyzed using a Likert scale and interpreted as serious, moderately serious, or least serious.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EXTENT OF TEACHING PRACTICES OF 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS ALONG WITH LEARNING SKILLS AS PERCEIVED BY THE TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 2 shows that the extent of teaching practices related to learning skills was sometimes observed by both Senior High School teachers and school heads, with an overall average weighted mean of 2.95. The highest-rated practices were organizing peer assessment or feedback sessions (AWM = 3.32) and encouraging respectful exchange of ideas (AWM = 3.31), indicating moderate integration of collaborative learning strategies.

Lower ratings were noted in breaking down complex tasks (AWM = 2.62) and monitoring self-directed learning (AWM = 2.68), suggesting areas for improvement. The close agreement between teachers and school heads reflects a consistent perception of the extent to which learning skills are practiced in the classroom.

Table 2
Extent of Teaching Practices of 21st-Century Skills along with Learning Skills as Perceived By The Teachers and School Heads

Learning Skills	Senior High School teachers		School heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	AWM	DE
1. Facilitate group activities to encourage participation and collaboration.	3.23	SO	3.21	SO	3.22	SO
2. Provide clear rubrics or performance standards to students.	2.83	SO	2.65	SO	2.74	SO
3. Help students synthesize and interpret information through guided questions.	2.65	SO	3.26	SO	2.96	SO
4. Encourage respectful exchange of ideas and opinions in class.	3.26	SO	3.35	SO	3.31	SO
5. Use graphic organizers to simplify complex topics.	3.35	SO	2.62	SO	2.99	SO
6. Monitor and support students during self-directed learning.	2.62	SO	2.73	SO	2.68	SO
7. Guide students in evaluating sources for reliability and bias.	2.73	SO	2.65	SO	2.69	SO
8. Break down complex tasks into smaller, manageable steps.	2.65	SO	2.59	SO	2.62	SO
9. Organize peer assessment or feedback sessions among students.	3.26	SO	3.37	SO	3.32	SO
Total	2.95	SO	2.94	SO	2.95	SO

EXTENT OF PRACTICES OF TEACHING 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS ALONG WITH THE INNOVATION SKILLS AS PERCEIVED BY THE TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 3 presents the extent of teaching practices related to innovation skills as perceived by Senior High School teachers and school heads. The overall average weighted mean of 3.09 indicates that innovation skills were sometimes observed in classroom instruction.

The highest-rated practice was promoting brainstorming sessions to encourage idea generation (AWM = 3.38), followed by integrating simulations or models to support experimentation (AWM = 3.28) and encouraging student-led projects or presentations (AWM = 3.27). These results suggest that opportunities for creativity and idea development are moderately incorporated into teaching practices.

Lower ratings were noted in designing project-based learning tasks related to real-world problems (AWM = 2.70) and encouraging exploration of multiple solutions and reflection on ideas (AWM = 2.89), indicating areas that may require further emphasis. The similar perceptions of teachers and school heads reflect a consistent view of the extent to which innovation skills are practiced in Senior High School classrooms.

Table 3
Extent of Teaching Practices of 21st-Century Skills Along with Innovation Skills as Perceived by The Teachers and School Heads

Innovation Skills	Senior High School teachers		School heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	AWM	DE
1. Design project-based learning tasks related to real-world problems.	2.62	SO	2.78	SO	2.70	SO
2. Promote brainstorming sessions to encourage idea generation.	3.35	SO	3.40	SO	3.38	SO
3. Empower students to improve their work through feedback.	3.23	SO	3.25	SO	3.24	SO
4. Encourage exploration of multiple solutions to a problem.	2.87	SO	2.91	SO	2.89	SO
5. Integrate simulations or models to support experimentation.	3.3	SO	3.25	SO	3.28	SO
6. Allow students to reflect on and revise their ideas.	2.87	SO	2.91	SO	2.89	SO
7. Encourage innovation through student-led projects or presentations.	3.22	SO	3.31	SO	3.27	SO
8. Provide scenarios for students to apply creativity in problem-solving.	3.02	SO	3.15	SO	3.09	SO
Total	3.06	SO	3.12	SO	3.09	SO

EXTENT OF PRACTICES OF TEACHING 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS ALONG WITH INFORMATION AND MEDIA SKILLS AS PERCEIVED BY THE TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 4 shows that the extent of teaching practices related to information and media skills was sometimes observed by both Senior High School teachers and school heads, with an overall average weighted mean of 3.06, indicating moderate integration of these skills in classroom instruction.

The highest-rated practices were the use of multiple media formats in delivering lessons (AWM = 3.32) and teaching students how to gather credible information from various sources (AWM = 3.30). Integrating news or current events into discussions (AWM = 3.23) and allowing students to creatively repackage information (AWM = 3.15) were also moderately practiced. Lower ratings were observed in encouraging collaborative work to synthesize information (AWM = 2.75) and using digital media to update students on current educational trends (AWM = 2.73), indicating areas that may require further enhancement.

The similar perceptions of teachers and school heads suggest a shared understanding of the extent to which information and media skills are implemented. The findings imply that while teachers moderately incorporate media and information literacy in their instruction, there is a need to further develop collaborative and digital practices. Strengthening these areas can enhance students' critical thinking, media literacy, and ability to navigate information effectively—essential competencies for 21st-century learning.

Table 4
Extent of Teaching Practices of 21st-Century Skills along with Information and Media Skills as Perceived by The Teachers and School Heads

Information and Media Skills	Senior High School teachers		School heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	AWM	DE
1. Use multiple media formats (e.g., videos, articles) to deliver lessons.	3.35	SO	3.29	SO	3.32	SO
2. Teach students how to gather credible information from various sources.	3.23	SO	3.36	SO	3.30	SO
3. Help students identify and challenge media bias and misinformation.	3.11	SO	3.17	SO	3.14	SO
4. Integrate news or current events into discussions.	3.24	SO	3.21	SO	3.23	SO

5. Encourage collaborative work to synthesize information.	3.23	SO	2.26	SO	2.75	SO
6. Allow students to repackage information creatively (e.g., infographics, skits).	3.23	SO	3.06	SO	3.15	SO
7. Use digital media to update students on current educational trends.	2.71	SO	2.75	SO	2.73	SO
8. Assist students in evaluating different perspectives in media sources.	2.82	SO	2.86	SO	2.84	SO
Total	3.12	SO	2.99	SO	3.06	SO

EXTENT OF PRACTICES OF THE TEACHING 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS ALONG WITH DIGITAL LITERACY SKILLS AS PERCEIVED BY THE TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 5 shows the extent of teaching practices related to digital literacy skills as perceived by Senior High School teachers and school heads. The overall average weighted mean of 3.30 indicates that digital literacy skills were sometimes observed in classroom practices.

The highest-rated practices were using digital tools to deliver lessons (AWM = 4.15), assigning online tasks to encourage responsible digital participation (AWM = 3.45), submitting reports and grades using digital platforms (AWM = 3.52), and using the internet as a tool for student assessments (AWM = 3.43), indicating strong adoption of some digital practices.

Lower ratings were observed in training students to use basic computer applications (AWM = 2.85), using interactive software to engage learners (AWM = 2.74), creating digital learning materials tailored to student needs (AWM = 3.08), and integrating ICT tools into everyday instruction (AWM = 3.17), suggesting areas for further professional development and support.

The similar perceptions of teachers and school heads reflect a shared understanding of the implementation of digital literacy skills. These findings imply that while teachers are integrating certain digital tools effectively, there is a need to strengthen students' digital competencies through guided instruction, interactive learning software, and consistent use of ICT in daily teaching, which are critical for preparing learners for the demands of 21st-century education.

Table 5
Extent of Teaching Practices of 21st-Century Skills Along with Digital Literacy Skills as Perceived By The Teachers and School Heads

Digital Literacy Skills	Senior High School Teachers	School Heads	Overall

	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	AWM	DE
1. Use digital tools to deliver lessons	4.11	O	4.19	O	4.15	O
2. Train students to use basic computer applications for learning.	2.71	SO	2.98	SO	2.85	SO
3. Assign online tasks to encourage responsible digital participation.	3.42	O	3.48	O	3.45	O
4. Submit reports and grades using digital platforms.	3.50	O	3.53	O	3.52	O
5. Use the internet as a tool for student assessments.	3.4	O	3.45	O	3.43	O
6. Create digital learning materials tailored to student needs.	3.01	SO	3.15	SO	3.08	SO
7. Use interactive software to engage learners.	2.67	SO	2.81	SO	2.74	SO
8. Integrate ICT tools into everyday instruction.	3.05	SO	3.28	SO	3.17	SO
9. Guide students in navigating digital learning environments.	3.23	SO	3.34	SO	3.29	SO
Total	3.23	SO	3.36	SO	3.30	SO

EXTENT OF PRACTICES OF THE TEACHING 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS ALONG WITH LIFE SKILLS AS PERCEIVED BY THE TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 6 presents the extent of teaching practices related to life skills as perceived by Senior High School teachers and school heads. The overall average weighted mean of 2.97 indicates that life skills were sometimes observed in classroom instruction.

The highest-rated practices included adapting well to changing classroom conditions or policies (AWM = 3.28) and building harmonious relationships with students and colleagues (AWM = 3.17), suggesting moderate attention to adaptability and interpersonal skills. Practices such as promoting respect for different cultures and beliefs (AWM = 2.95) and supporting peaceful conflict resolution (AWM = 2.95) were also moderately practiced.

Lower ratings were observed in addressing students' individual learning needs sensitively (AWM = 2.69) and reflecting on personal and professional experiences for growth (AWM = 2.62), indicating areas that may need further development.

The similar perceptions of teachers and school heads reflect a consistent understanding of life skills implementation. These findings imply that while teachers moderately promote interpersonal and adaptive skills, additional focus on individualized support, self-reflection, and conflict management strategies is necessary to fully prepare learners for personal, social, and professional challenges in the 21st century.

Table 6
Extent of Teaching Practices of 21st-Century Skills Along with Life Skills as Perceived by The Teachers and School Heads

Life Skills	Senior High School Teachers		School Heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	AWM	DE
1. Promote respect for different cultures and beliefs.	2.91	SO	2.98	SO	2.95	SO
2. Build harmonious relationships with students and colleagues.	3.11	SO	3.23	SO	3.17	SO
3. Adapt well to changing classroom conditions or policies.	3.35	SO	3.21	SO	3.28	SO
4. Address students' individual learning needs sensitively.	3.12	SO	2.25	SO	2.69	SO
5. Encourage cooperation rather than competition.	3.05	SO	3.02	SO	3.04	SO
6. Reflect on personal and professional experiences for growth.	2.79	SO	2.45	SO	2.62	SO
7. Support peaceful conflict resolution in the classroom.	2.95	SO	2.94	SO	2.95	SO
8. Maintain balance in handling diverse classroom dynamics.	3.02	SO	3.15	SO	3.09	SO
Total	3.04	SO	2.90	SO	2.97	SO

EXTENT OF PRACTICES OF THE TEACHING 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS ALONG WITH CAREER SKILLS AS PERCEIVED BY THE TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 7 shows the extent of teaching practices related to career skills as perceived by Senior High School teachers and school heads. The overall average weighted mean of 3.04 indicates that career skills were sometimes observed in classroom practices.

The highest-rated practices included demonstrating strong time and task management skills (AWM = 3.49) and practicing professionalism in fulfilling job responsibilities (AWM = 3.25), suggesting that teachers moderately exhibit essential workplace competencies.

Lower ratings were observed in participating in professional development and training (AWM = 2.80), continuing to learn to improve subject matter expertise (AWM = 2.91), and documenting and managing classroom issues effectively (AWM = 2.85), highlighting areas that require further attention.

The similar perceptions of teachers and school heads suggest a shared understanding of career skills implementation. These findings imply that while teachers demonstrate professionalism and organizational skills, there is a need to strengthen ongoing professional development, reflective practice, and management of classroom documentation to fully prepare learners for career readiness in the 21st century.

Table 7
Extent of Practices of Teaching 21st-Century Skills along with Career Skills as Perceived by The Teachers and School Heads

Career Skills	Senior High School Teachers		School Heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	AWM	DE
1. Demonstrate strong time and task management skills.	3.41	O	3.56	O	3.49	O
2. Continue learning to improve expertise in subject matter.	2.89	SO	2.93	SO	2.91	SO
3. Participate in professional development and training.	2.78	SO	2.82	SO	2.80	SO
4. Develop learning activities that reflect diverse student backgrounds.	3.04	SO	3.24	SO	2.98	SO
5. Select instructional materials that meet various learner needs.	2.89	SO	2.78	SO	2.84	SO
6. Maintain accurate and updated student records.	3.01	SO	3.15	SO	3.08	SO
7. Document and manage classroom issues effectively.	2.67	SO	3.02	SO	2.85	SO
8. Practice professionalism in fulfilling job responsibilities.	3.21	O	3.28	O	3.25	SO
Total	2.99	SO	3.10	SO	3.04	SO

SUMMARY OF THE EXTENT OF PRACTICES OF THE TEACHING 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS AS PERCEIVED BY THE TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 8 summarizes the extent of practices of teaching 21st-century skills as perceived by Senior High School teachers and school heads. The overall average weighted mean of 3.07 indicates that the integration of 21st-century skills in classrooms was sometimes observed.

Among the skill domains, **digital literacy skills** received the highest rating (AWM = 3.30), suggesting that teachers are moderately incorporating technology and digital tools into instruction. **Innovation skills** (AWM = 3.09) and **information and media skills** (AWM = 3.06) were also moderately practiced, reflecting some engagement in creative, collaborative, and information-driven activities.

Lower ratings were observed in **learning skills** (AWM = 2.95) and **life skills** (AWM = 2.97), indicating that practices related to collaboration, critical thinking, adaptability, and interpersonal development need further strengthening. **Career skills** were moderately observed (AWM = 3.04), with teachers showing professionalism and task management, though professional development and reflective practices require enhancement.

These findings imply that while Senior High School teachers moderately implement 21st-century skills, there is a need for targeted interventions, professional development, and resource support to strengthen teaching practices across all domains and better prepare learners for the demands of the 21st-century workplace and society.

Table 8
Summary of the Extent of Practices of Teaching 21st-century skills as Perceived by the Teachers and School Heads

Teaching 21st-century skills	Senior High School Teachers		School Heads		Overall	
	Weighted Mean	DE	Weighted Mean	DE	Average Weighted Mean	DE
1. Learning Skills	2.95	SO	2.94	SO	2.95	SO
2. Innovation Skills	3.06	SO	3.12	SO	3.09	SO

3. Information and Media Skills	3.12	SO	2.99	SO	3.06	SO
4. Digital Literacy Skills	3.23	SO	3.36	SO	3.30	SO
5. Life Skills	3.04	SO	2.90	SO	2.97	SO
6. Career Skills	2.99	SO	3.10	SO	3.04	SO
Total	3.06	SO	3.07	SO	3.07	SO

DIFFERENCES IN THE EXTENT OF TEACHING PRACTICES OF 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS BETWEEN THE TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 9 presents the comparison of the extent of teaching practices of 21st-century skills between Senior High School teachers and school heads. The overall weighted means show that both groups sometimes observed these practices, with teachers averaging 3.06 and school heads 3.07.

The computed t -value of 0.4737 ($df = 5$) is lower than the critical value of 2.015 at the 0.05 level of significance. Based on this, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating **no significant difference** between the perceptions of teachers and school heads regarding the extent of teaching practices of 21st-century skills.

This finding implies that both teachers and school heads share a consistent understanding of how 21st-century skills are integrated into classroom instruction, reflecting alignment between instructional implementation and supervisory observation.

Table 9
Significance Differences in the Extent of Teaching Practices of 21st-century skills
Between the Teachers and School Heads

	Senior High School Teachers	School Heads
Teaching 21st-century skills		

	Weighted Mean	DE	Weighted Mean	DE
1. Learning Skills	2.95	SO	2.94	SO
2. Innovation Skills	3.06	SO	3.12	SO
3. Information and Media Skills	3.12	SO	2.99	SO
4. Digital Literacy Skills	3.23	SO	3.36	SO
5. Life Skills	3.04	SO	2.90	SO
6. Career Skills	2.99	SO	3.10	SO
Total	3.06	SO	3.07	SO

Computed *t*-value: 0.4737@ *df* 5
 Alpha: @ 0.05 extent of practices of significance
 Critical Value: 2.0150, *df* 5
 Decision: accept the null hypothesis
 Interpretation: No significant difference

EXTENT OF SERIOUSNESS OF PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY TEACHERS

Table 10 presents the degree of seriousness of problems encountered by teachers in implementing 21st-century teaching practices. The overall mean of 2.21 indicates that the problems were moderately serious (MS).

The most serious problem identified was limited exposure to updated training focused on 21st-century teaching approaches (Mean = 2.59, Rank 1), followed by difficulty designing innovative, student-centered learning due to large class sizes and multiple teaching loads (Mean = 2.54, Rank 2) and lack of ICT equipment and digital tools in schools (Mean = 2.34, Rank 3). Low student engagement and motivation was also a notable concern (Mean = 2.24, Rank 4).

Less serious problems included rigid or numerous learning competencies (Mean = 2.06, Rank 7), misaligned instructional materials (Mean = 2.03, Rank 9), and resistance to change (Mean = 1.88, Rank 10).

These findings imply that while teachers moderately experience challenges in integrating 21st-century skills, targeted interventions are needed, particularly in professional development, access to ICT resources, and strategies for managing large classes and motivating students. Addressing these issues can enhance the effective implementation of 21st-century teaching practices.

Table 10
Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered

Indicators	Teachers		Rank
	Mean	DE	
1. Limited exposure to updated training focused on 21st-century teaching approaches.	2.59	S	1
2. Lack of ICT equipment (computers, projectors, internet access) and digital tools in schools	2.34	S	3
3. Teachers often struggle to design innovative and student-centered learning experiences due to Large class sizes and Multiple teaching loads	2.54	S	2
4. Learning competencies are too numerous or rigid	2.06	MS	7
5. Some students lack foundational skills (e.g., reading comprehension, basic tech skills)	2.29	MS	5
6. Low Student Engagement and Motivation	2.24	S	4
7. Learning modules, textbooks, and instructional materials may not align with the goals of 21st-century education	2.03	MS	9
8. Limited support from leadership,	2.16	MS	6
9. Unclear implementation guidelines	2.05	MS	8
10. Resistance to change	1.88	MS	10
Total	2.21	MS	

Conclusion

The study revealed that the extent of teaching 21st-century skills among Senior High School teachers in District V-A, San Carlos City Division, is generally sometimes observed across key domains, including learning skills, innovation skills, information and media skills, digital literacy skills, life skills, and career skills. Both teachers and school heads shared similar perceptions, indicating consistency in how the integration of 21st-century skills is implemented and observed

across classrooms. Challenges encountered in teaching these skills were rated as moderately serious, highlighting areas that require additional support and intervention.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that professional development programs be strengthened to enhance teachers' capacity in implementing student-centered, innovative, and technology-integrated instruction. Schools should provide adequate ICT resources and digital tools, promote collaborative and reflective teaching practices, and support strategies that increase student engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving. An action plan focused on targeted training, resource provision, and instructional support should be implemented to improve the consistent integration of 21st-century skills across classrooms.

For future research, studies could examine the long-term impact of 21st-century skills instruction on student academic performance, digital competence, and career readiness. Comparative studies between schools with high and low integration of 21st-century practices could also provide valuable insights into effective strategies for preparing learners to meet the demands of the 21st-century workplace and society.

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